

METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS DEVELOPMENT TECHNOLOGIES.

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Annotation: In this article, the main directions of the formation of the issues of the development of the competence of teachers are defined, the concepts of professional and methodical competence are defined, and the qualities of a specialist with professional competence are described in detail. At the same time, the main requirements that ensure the necessary and sufficient level of preparation of future teachers for pedagogical activity are also highlighted.

Key words: competence, professional competence, innovative form of teaching, spirituality, excellence, scientific activity.

Аннотация: В данной статье определены основные направления формирования вопросов развития компетентности педагогов, определены понятия профессионально-методической компетентности, подробно описаны качества специалиста, обладающего профессиональной компетентностью. При этом также выделены основные требования, обеспечивающие необходимый и достаточный уровень подготовки будущих учителей к педагогической деятельности.

Ключевые слова: компетентность, профессиональная компетентность, инновационная форма обучения, духовность, мастерство, научная

Anontatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o`qituvchilarning kompetentligini rivojlantirish masalalarini shakllantirish asosiy yo`nalishlarini kasbiy va metodik kompetentlik tushunchalariga ta`rif berilgan, shuningdek, kasbiy kompetensiyaga ega mutaxassisning sifatlari haqida batafsil bayon etilgan. Shu bilan birga bo`lajak

o'qituvchilarning pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorgarligining zaruriy va yetarli darajasini ta'minlab beruvchi asosiy talablar ham yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar:kompetentlik, kasbiy kompetentlik, o'qitishning innovatsion shakli, ma'naviyat ,mukammallik, faoliyatining ilmiyligi.

Processes of training highly qualified pedagogic personnel that meet the requirements of the time are the main requirements of the international labor market today. The reason is that society needs people who think independently, who can express themselves, and who can make an objective assessment of themselves. They are the driving forces of the development of society. This, in turn, creates the need to update the content of continuous education that serves to develop the professional competence of specialists, to widely introduce innovative forms and methods of teaching, modern information and communication technologies, and advanced foreign experiences in teaching. Based on this, a number of measures are being implemented in educational institutions to improve the quality of education, to ensure the coherence and continuity of educational stages. It is known that modernizing the educational process in educational institutions, developing the professional competence of teachers in improving the quality of the system of training pedagogues, using modern advanced foreign experiences in the field, professional knowledge, skills and vision Arming with skills, independent creative use of scientific and technical innovations, and development of skills to solve prospective tasks are considered important tasks. In this place, it is necessary to pay special attention to the professional competence of future teachers and their analytical skills. Professional competence, professional self-awareness, respect for professional values and orientation to the profession - this is universal, which is manifested in the example of the professional formation of the young generation, support and development of innate abilities. generalizing concepts that are one of the components of culture. The formation of professional competencies of future teachers is to ensure that they act successfully on the basis

of practical experience and knowledge in solving professional issues. Realization of professional competence and professional identity is considered a lifelong process, a person chooses a profession from the stages of dreaming, trying, choosing and realizing them, then he enters a profession, and later changes professions in the world, in his own changes his profession or specialty depending on the change, his attitude to work. The idea of a perfect person is a noble idea of both national and universal importance, which embodies spiritual and physical perfection and motivates a person towards noble goals. Perfection should be embodied in the image of a modern teacher. Forming the professional competence of today's teacher is to increase his daily ability and work efficiency. It is possible to train qualified specialists by studying and solving problems related to the formation of professional skills in work activities, forming professional training. The need to improve the pedagogical and psychological knowledge of future teachers is based on the growth of social demands placed on educational institutions and teachers. In the field of higher education, determination of the actual needs for education is carried out based on the determination of the level of their professional training, the aspects that meet the requirements, as well as the existing shortcomings and gaps. Based on this, it is appropriate to implement innovations. This leads to the development of pedagogical competence. Another important aspect of the educational process is the organization of students' educational activities based on their interests and directed to the personality of the student. These include students' interest in learning, their sense of duty, and methods of forming responsibility in the educational process. Organization and coordination of cooperative activities of subjects in the improvement of pedagogical processes, the effectiveness of developing their activity in the direction of the goals that need to be achieved depends to a large extent on existing motives and motivation. The field of education is a social institution that reflects all the problems of society. In modern education, it is necessary to enrich and

improve spiritual and educational values, to humanize it through the educational process, to activate educational activities with spiritual and educational growth, to provide pedagogical and psychological support. It is necessary to educate highly moral, responsible, creative, competent citizens through support. The spiritual and educational development of a person is the main issue of current education, and for this, the teacher must have a high level of spiritual and educational competence. Spirituality is a manifestation of qualities related to the enrichment of the inner world, aimed at opening up one's personal potential. Spirituality is a description of self-awareness as a person, reflecting perfection and balance of the inner world. It is necessary to convey clear visions of spirituality to the next generation, which is considered the main criterion that ensures our material and spiritual well-being. Spiritual and educational development is self-creation and development as a manifestation of behavior aimed at oneself and others. The development of spiritual-educational competence is formed during personal development, the existence of a spiritual-educational model (in the form of parents, teachers), and the implementation of the educational process based on universal human values integrated into the educational program. Spiritual and educational development - a person's assimilation of sources of national and religious values, attitude of traditional moral standards and spiritual ideals towards himself, others, the state and the world as a whole; it is carried out through educational tools in the organized educational process. The spiritual sources of spirituality are based on love for people, success in life and high values. The scientific nature of teachers' activities is the search for, learning and basing on new information, the use of scientifically based information, the organization and management of pedagogical processes, pedagogical, psychological and social. -determines tasks such as mastering the economic foundations, including the introduction of innovative approach technologies to pedagogical processes.

In conclusion, it should be noted that introducing future teachers to various methods of organizing and managing pedagogical processes, developing their professional competence, arming them with the secrets of professional skills, and forming a methodology for working with pedagogical innovations is one of the important factors that increase the effectiveness of education. is considered In order to ensure the effectiveness of pedagogical processes, future teachers should have knowledge of strategic planning, design, modeling of pedagogical processes, coordination of student activities and ensuring their activity, methods, methods and principles of pedagogical process management according to situations, innovative technologies and based on them, it is necessary to form the skills of organizing the innovative activities of the subjects of the pedagogical process.

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